

Stone Bunds For Soil and Water Conservation

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Introduction

Natural resources like soil and water are under serious threat due to intensive agriculture which is intended to increase the world's food production. But, sustainable food production for the future generation becomes challenging due to soil and water quality deterioration. Soil erosion is one of the significant problems which decreases soil health and crop production. Anthropogenic activities coupled with climate change further worsen the condition. Rainfall/precipitation, topography, vegetation and soil property are the major factors contributing to soil erosion. The worldwide annual rate of soil erosion from agricultural land ranges from 22 to 100-ton ha⁻¹, which results in 15–30% loss of agricultural productivity.

Cultivation of crops on higher slopes, ploughing along the slope, intensive cultivation and excessive chemical inputs also accelerate soil erosion problems in agricultural lands. Changing rainfall patterns and intensities will substantially increase the risk of runoff, soil erosion, drought and other land degradation problems in the future. Scientists have recommended many soil conservation techniques to control soil erosion according to the slope, soil type and crops. Hence, adopting suitable soil and moisture conservation measures may mitigate climate change impacts. The stone bund is a well-recognized soil and water conservation technique to control runoff and soil erosion from agricultural fields with less than 10 % slope. Stone bunds are an indispensable soil and moisture conservation technique to increase production in semiarid regions. This technology's moisture conserving benefits are critical in drier areas.

Stone Bunds as soil and water conservation structure

The stone bund is an embankment constructed from locally available stones along the contour and stabilized with a ditch at the upper side to check the soil erosion and runoff from the agricultural lands. The stone bunds are a viable and economical soil conservation structure where stones are available locally or on nearby premises. They are very effective in soil and moisture conservation in agricultural lands with gentle, undulating slopes with moderate soil depth. Durability and compatibility with cultural operations are the unique features of the stone bunds. In drylands, nutrient use efficiency is very low due to poor soil moisture conditions. The in-situ soil

moisture conservation practices like bunds can conserve the rainwater in the field and optimize the nutrient use efficiency through water and nutrient interactions.

Stone bunds for tea plantations

India is one of the major contributors to world tea production. In India, tea is grown at elevations varying from 600 to 1,800 meters above sea level. It requires 1500-3000 mm of annual rainfall distributed throughout the year. Although it requires a high amount of water, excess water stagnation affects root growth and production. Hence, tea is mainly cultivated on hill slopes to facilitate drainage. As nature favors tea cultivation in high rainfall and hilly regions, soil erosion is an inevitable problem in tea cultivation, specifically in young tea plantations. Tea being a perennial crop, should be protected against high rainfall with a permanent engineering structure. Hence stone bunding is recommended in tea plantations as an erosion control measure.

Plate 1. Stone bunds in tea plantations constructed with locally available stones

Plate 2. Stone bunds constructed in tea plantation along with silver oak tree

Stone bunds for agricultural field

The construction of stone bunds can alter erosion and sedimentation processes along slopes. Stone bunds influence infiltration and runoff processes, soil water dynamics, crop growth and yield. The stone bunds in sloppy agricultural lands form a barrier and reduce the runoff velocity, allowing rainwater to infiltrate the soil. Soil's physical and chemical properties also improved in the interspace between two bunds where crops are cultivated. Stone bunds constructed along the contour are called contour stone bunds. These CSB act as a sink and trap the sediment and runoff in the field. The efficiency of the stone bunds depends on the distance between the two bunds. Hence the vertical interval between two bunds has to be decided by following the proper design criteria. Periodical removal of deposited sediment also helps improve stone bunds' efficiency.

Plate 3. Stone Bund in Agricultural Land

Recommended Specifications

Contour Stone Bunds needs to be built with on-site available stone material ranging from 30 to 40 cm in height and 30 to 40 cm in width. The distance (Horizontal Interval) between stone depends on the slope, but they normally range from 10 to 50 m (recommended slope is 6 % to 60 %).

Advantages of stone bunds as soil and water conservation structures

- Stone bunds can perform the dual role of soil erosion control measures during heavy rains and in-situ moisture conservation measures during drought.
- Water retention in soil is important for crop growth especially in short dry spells during the rainy season
- Enhanced soil moisture content ensures the soil microbial diversity and nutrient dynamics.
- Enhance the plant growth and yield in result of higher soil and nutrient retention capacity

Conclusion

Under climate change mitigation measures, stone bunds can protect the land from extreme events like floods and drought. During heavy rains, they will help to reduce the runoff, and during the drought, they improve rainwater harvesting, retention and infiltration into the soil. Stone bunds enhance the interactions of soil, water and nutrients results the increased production and soil health. Field with stone bunds can increase the yield to 2-3 times than field without stone bunds. However any soil and water conservation measures needs a long gestation period to realize their impact on crop productivity. Hence, farmers should be educated to enhance their understanding of ecosystem services and encourage collective action to counter land degradation through such soil and water conservation measures.

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